

Synthesis of some new thiocarbamides from a constituent of lac and studies on their antimicrobial activities

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Some new thiocarbamides have been synthesized by the reaction of aleurityl hydrazide (prepared from aleuritic acid isolated from Bangladeshi lac) with different isothiocyanates. Antibacterial activities of the compounds have been determined and most of them are found highly active.

Arylthiocarbamides find various industrial¹ and biological² uses. S, N-containing heterocyclic compounds are also possess varied biological activities³.

Here we report the synthesis of some new thiocarbamides by the reaction of aleurityl hydrazide (prepared from aleuritic acid, the chief constituent of lac) with different isothiocyanates. Antibacterial property of these compounds has also been tested.

Results and Discussion

The composition of different varieties of lac obtained from Baisakhi crop produced in BCSIR Laboratories, Rajshahi, by the Ranginee type of insects on the host ber tree (*Zizyphus jujuba*) were determined⁴ and the results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Composition (%) of Bangladeshi stick lac, seed lac, shellac, dewaxed shellac and bleached lac

Component	Stick lac	Seed lac	Shellac	Dewaxed shellac	Bleached lac
Resin	70.87	82.25	87.60	91.95	88.95
Dye	10.00	2.50	1.50	1.12	Nil
Wax	8.54	6.00	5.50	0.10	3.55
Foreign bodies	4.00	1.75	Nil	Nil	Nil
Insolubles in hot alcohol	2.50	1.80	1.50	0.10	1.10
Moisture	2.01	2.00	1.90	1.52	1.75
Ash	1.37	1.55	0.90	0.15	0.44

Aleuritic acid was isolated from shellac to an extent of 30% following the reported procedure⁵. It was esterified with anhydrous methanol using HCl as catalyst. The resulting methyl aleuritate was converted to the acid hydrazide

by the action of hydrazine hydrate⁶. The reaction of aleuritylhydrazide with several alkyl or arylisothiocyanates in boiling benzene afforded the thiocarbamides (1).

1-Substituted-3-N-aleuritamidothiocarbamides (1)
where R is the aleuritic acid residue and R' = *t*-Bu, Ph, *p*-tolyl, *p*-anisyl, T.A.G (1-tetraacetylglucosyl)

Antibacterial activities of the thiocarbamides were determined by paper-disc method⁷ against the following 16 pathogenic bacteria : *Bacillus subtilis* (BTCC 17), *B. cereus* (BTCCC 19), *B. megaterium* (BTCC 18), *Sarcina lutea* (ATCC 9341), *Streptococcus β-haemolyticus* (BTCC 525), *S. aureus* (ATCC 25923), *S. dysenteriae* (BTCC 526), *S. shiga* (BTCC 27), *S. flexneriae*, *S. boydii* (13147), *S. sonnei* (BTCC 528), *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922), *Salmonella typhi* A (CRL), *S. typhi* B (CRL), *S. typhi* B-56 (CRL), *Klebsiella* species. The compounds showed enhanced activity against all the pathogens. Only few pathogens such as *E. coli* (ATCC 25922) and *Klebsiella* species did not show any inhibition with the thiocarbamide, *t*-Bu.T. Similarly, the pathogens such as *S. shiga* (BTCC 27) and *E. coli* (ATCC 25922), *S. typhi* B (CRL) and *S. typhi* B-56 (CRL), *S. boydii* (13147), *S. typhi* A (CRL) and *S. typhi* B-56 (CRL) and also *S. sonnei* (BTCC 528) did not show any inhibition with thiocarbamides, P.T, *p*-T.T, *p*-A.T and T.A.G.T, respectively. The zone of inhibition was

found to vary from 4 to 14 mm. The present result is satisfactory and compares well with the antibacterial activities of other thiocarbamides reported in the literature⁸.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The isothiocyanates were prepared by the reported method⁹ and their purity was checked by TLC. The lac was collected from the experimental garden of BCSIR Laboratories, Rajshahi. Stick lac was obtained by scrapping encrustation of lac from the twigs of lac host. Seed lac was obtained by crushing and washing of stick lac. Seed lac was subjected to hot filtration through cloth bag followed by hand-stretching to thin sheets and then crumbling to small pieces to give shellac. Wax (6.0%) was removed to give dewaxed shellac. The orange colour of seed lac was removed by sodium hypochlorite to get bleached lac.

Aleuritic acid (90%; m.p. 100–101°) was isolated from powdered dewaxed shellac by method reported earlier⁵. Aleurityl hydrazide (95%; m.p. 138–139°) was prepared from methyl aleuritate, and the latter (85%, m.p. 72–73°) was prepared from aleuritic acid by reported methods⁶.

t-Butylisothiocyanate : A mixture of freshly distilled *t*-butyl chloride (150 ml), an aqueous solution of ammonium thiocyanate (30 g) and zinc chloride (15 g) was allowed to stand for 15 days with occasional shaking. The upper pale yellow viscous dense layer that separated was washed with water. To this dense oil anhydrous zinc chloride (15 g) was added and again it was allowed to stand for another 7 days with occasional shaking. Finally, the product was washed with water, dried over anhyd. calcium chloride, distilled and the fraction between 138–140° was collected (yield 80 ml).

1-t-Butyl-3-*N*-aleuritamidothiocarbamide : To a benzene solution of aleurityl hydrazide (3.18 g in 50 ml) freshly prepared *t*-butyl isothiocyanate (1.15 g) was added. The mixture was shaken gently and refluxed for 2 h. On distilling of the solvent from the reaction mixture, the desired thiocarbamide was obtained as a white solid (1.4 g), crystallized from ethanol. It was designated as *t*-Bu.T., m.p. 85°. Its aqueous solution was found to be readily desulfurated when heated with alkaline plumbite solution, indicating the presence of –CS–NH– group. It was soluble in ethanol, acetone, benzene, dioxane and insoluble in water, ether; R_f 0.92 (benzene : acetone 1 : 1) (Found : N, 9.68; S, 7.30. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{43}N_3O_4S$: N, 9.70; S, 7.39%); v_{max} 3350 (OH), 3200 (NH), 2900 (CH_2), 1695 (C=O), 1550 (N–N), 1360 ($C(CH_3)_3$), 1320 (C–N), 1050 cm^{-1} (C=S).

Similarly, other thiocarbamides were prepared.

1-Phenyl-3-*N*-aleuritamidothiocarbamide (P.T.), m.p. 110–111° (Found : N, 9.15; S, 6.90. Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{39}N_3O_4S$: N, 9.27; S, 7.06%); R_f 0.95 (benzene : acetone, 1 : 1); v_{max} 3200 (OH), 3100 (NH), 2960 (CH_2), 1590 (C=O), 1400 (N–N), 1320 (C–N), 1095 cm^{-1} (C=S). *1*-*p*-Tolyl-3-*N*-aleuritamidothiocarbamide (*p*-T.T.), m.p. 96–97° (Found : N, 8.50; S, 6.35. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{41}N_3O_4S$: N, 8.99; S, 6.85%); R_f 0.80 (benzene : acetone, 1 : 1); v_{max} 3400 (OH), 3150 (NH), 2950 (CH_2), 1590 (C=O), 1470 (N–N), 1250 (C–N), 1140 cm^{-1} (C=S). *1*-*p*-Anisyl-3-*N*-aleuritamidothiocarbamide (*p*-A.T.), m.p. 115–116° (Found : N, 8.55; S, 6.50. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{41}N_3O_5S$: N, 8.70; S, 6.63%); R_f 0.90 (benzene : acetone, 1 : 1); v_{max} 3250 (OH), 3250 (NH), 2900 (CH_2), 1675 (C=O), 1440 (N–N), 1295 (C–N), 1100 cm^{-1} (C=S). *1*-Tetra-acetylglucosyl-3-*N*-aleuritamidothiocarbamide (T.A.G.T.), m.p. 102–103° (Found : N, 5.75; S, 4.30. Calcd. for $C_{31}H_{53}N_3O_{13}S$: N, 5.94; S, 4.53%); R_f 0.90 (benzene : acetone, 1 : 1); v_{max} 3300 (OH), 3300 (NH), 2990 (CH_2), 1740 (C=O), 1510 (N–N), 1350 (C–N), 1050 cm^{-1} (C=S).

Antibacterial activities of the thiocarbamides were determined by paper-disc method⁷ in concentration range, 10 μ L containing 30 μ g.

References

- Ch. L. Melamed, G. A. Blokh, A. P. Grishchuk, S. N. Baranov and Yu. R. Ebich, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, **72**, 32954; Ch. L. Melamed, A. P. Grishchuk and G. A. Block, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, **72**, 56504.
- W. J. Considine, US Pat. 3597440/1917 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, **75**, 110223).
- M. U. Ali, M. Z. Haque and M. M. Islam, *J. Bangladesh Acad. Sci.*, 1997, **21**, 165; M. U. Ali, M. M. Islam and M. Z. Haque, *J. Bangladesh Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **9**, 215; M. S. Rahman, M. U. Ali and M. Z. Haque, *J. Bangladesh Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **10**, 154.
- M. O. Faruq, M. I. H. Khan, M. M. Alam, M. Z. Haque, M. M. Rahman and M. A. Rahman, *Bangladesh J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1990, **25**, 206.
- M. Z. Haque, M. O. Faruq and M. U. Ali, *J. Bangladesh Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **10**, 93.
- A. L. Davis and W. H. Gardner, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1902.
- A. W. Beur, W. M. M. Kirby, J. C. Sherris and M. Turek, *Am. J. Clin. Pathol.*, 1966, **44**, 493.
- H. K. Shukla, N. C. Desai, R. R. Astik and K. A. Thaker, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **61**, 168; S. V. Patel, G. V. Bhadani and G. B. Joshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **61**, 169.
- H. Gilman and A. H. Blant, *Org. Synth.*, 1967, **1**, 447.